

M edico-Legal Talk

Medico-Legal Issues in Clinical Dental Practice

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Herewith, I am happy to write a column on the subject of Medico-Legal issues in Clinical Dental Practice. Initiatives taken by the Editorial Board and the publisher to start publishing this column in this esteemed Dental Journal - Heal Talk is appreciable. I extend my sincere thanks to the administrator of this Dental Journal - Heal Talk for giving me golden opportunity to write on this medicolegal column.

Introduction: This introductory medico-legal article will give readers a brief, general idea about various challenges in day to day Dental Clinical practice. Subsequently, I am going to write articles and discuss various medico-legal issues arising out of Dentist-patients disputes. With this opportunity, I assure to the readers of this Journal, that I will try my best to throw lights on valuable medico-legal issues with the help of various Laws of Land and Judicial Judgments at District level, State level and National level. This column will discuss various issues related to Dentist, Dental Clinical Practice and Governing Laws, Rules, Regulations, guidelines laid down by the Legislatures, Apex bodies like DCI, MCI, IDA, IMA and Judiciary through their judicial decisions. I hope that this column will definitely be very informative and useful for understanding the concepts of Law in Dental practice. Hence, Dentists will get help to make their practice litigation free.

Law and Health: To understand this subject, one must understand first: What is Law? and What is Health? Law is a body of rules or norms passed by a Legislated Authority and enforced by an Authorized and specialized body. Health of a person is physical well being or freedom of the disease. Modern concept of health is a state of total physical, mental and social well being.

The Scientific advances have changed almost all fields in human life. The Medical and Dental faculties are not exceptions to these changes. In day to day Dental Clinical practice the advances in materials used in Dental practice and their scientific use has brought the changes in diagnostic and clinical treatment protocols. Thus Dentist is expected to be updated with such advances and their appropriate scientific use in Dental Clinical practice in order to provide better health to the patient.

The Law and Medicine is a complex subject. Medico-legal issues means compilation of various issues related to Law and Medicine. Medico-legal issues crosses borders in various areas like Science, Health, Ethics, Philosophy, Technology, History and so on so forth. In this modern time with newer and newer development, day by day this medico-legal discipline also connected to Civil Law, Criminal Law, Torts, Consumer Law, Public Health Law, Professional Ethics and many more Laws regarding medical and scientific matters. Understanding of this medico-legal issues is important to Dentists. At the same time the lawyer should also understand the intricacies of medical sciences and health.

Consent, History evaluation & Documentations, Treatment with requisite qualification & experience without Negligence: First of all the Dentist must take required Consent from the patient as per law. While providing the treatment with these advances, the Dentist should not be negligent. Dentist must have requisite qualification as per law and should be aware about the various properties of the materials with reasonable experience to handle it. So that these materials may not affect the health of patients adversely in any aspects.

Hence, the thorough evaluation of clinical history, in respects of general health of the patients must be evaluated and documented in patients case records. Such evaluated history and documented records must be preserved by the Dentists in accordance with law in force. These advances, evaluation of clinical history and their documentations as per law also invites scrutiny and cross examination of the Dentist from Attorneys / Lawyers of the patients, Courts, professional boards and regulatory bodies.

Contributory Negligence: Like the Dentists, the patient is also expected to be diligent in her/his truthfulness and giving real medical history to the Dentist. The same should be documented by the Dentist. Maintaining proper record of documentation by the Dentist is utmost important. These records is very important as defense. If the action of the patients, like hiding of some crucial information such as taking medication for some medical ailments eg: Diabetes, Cardiovascular Disease, Allergy to some medications is responsible for causing the damage or has played role in increasing damage to the patient. Then such contributory negligent act as a defense for the Dentist.

The Dentists and patients rights and Duties, the action in good faith: The Indian Constitution and various Laws, Rules and Regulations has provided rights and duties for all citizen. So the Dentist and patients are not exceptions. If there is breach in the duties of the Dentist with negligence, and simultaneously rights of the patients are infringed. That has caused damage to the patients.

Liability: For the damage caused, the Dentists is liable in the Court of Law. But at the same time the action taken / the treatment procedure conducted by the Dentist in good faith with the due diligence is not actionable in the law.

“Ignorance of law can not be excuse”: Thus it is expected that both Dentists and patients must be aware of one’s rights and duties. In the Court of Law there is no excuse if someone is not aware about the Law of the Land. Everyone is expected to be aware about the various provisions of Laws, Rules, Regulations, Ethical Code of Conduct which one must follow. Thus the Dentist must be aware about Fundamental Rights and Duties of patients and Dentist, incorporated in Indian Constitution, salient features of Laws like Dentists Act of 1948, The Consumer Protection Act and its procedures, Medical and Dental Negligence, Informed consent, Legal procedure and Evidentiary requirements as per various laws in force.

Entry of Police, Lawyer and Media in Dental Clinical Practice: Thus in present digital technology and because of availability of tools like Google search, it became easy for the patient to search all information in one click. Most of the time because of easy availability of information to patients and simplicity of Consumer Forum procedures, the filing of disputes in Consumer Forum became easy and less expensive. Such negligence allegation and litigations filed by the patient against Dentist may give entry of Police, Advocate and Media in Dental Clinical practice which may spoil the image of Dentist in the society and may affects carrier adversely.

Doctor and Lawyer both are experts in their own concern subject but stranger to other discipline. So the thorough study of the subject “Law and Medicine” i.e. medico-legal issues is very important and crucial for delivering justice. The subject brings amalgamation of law and medicine together and helps both Doctor and Lawyer to understand both the subjects in better and appropriate manner. Thus, by understanding this subject, the Dentist can understand more about his accountability and responsibilities under the laws. Hence, the Dentist can defend himself in a better and most appropriate manner in a Court of Law. On the other hand the Lawyer, with the help of knowledge of medical science can testify or cross examine a Dentist in the Court of Law more effectively. Thus, this helps judiciary in making decision in order to make justice for both patient and Dentist.

Conclusion: Hence, the Dentist must be well aware about medico legal issues in depth. So that the Dentist will be cautious from entry of the patient in the Dental Clinic starting from consent, case history evaluation, documentation and record keeping, till the final steps of the treatment including follow up records wherever necessary as per case. Thus, the Dentist will maintain all relevant records for his defense for sufficient length of time. That will help the Dentist to defend his/her case or minimize litigations or make practice litigation free.